

Effects of Sea water pollution on Chicken Fetus

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Organic matters and heavy metals contamination in sea water obstruct vital functions of chicken fetus and interrupt its growth.

Histological examination of contaminated fetuses shows a menacing growth of abnormal protuberance on the lungs as well as highly impeded formation of capillaries, although lung-pipes exhibited normal expansion. Compared with the control, liver tissue also showed retarded growth accompanied by decrease in liver weight. Consequently, vital metabolic functions were impaired hydropsy and evisceration developed, and fetuses were deformed.

CONTAMINATING substances, contained in industrial effluent discharged into the sea affect animals and plants in an adverse way.¹⁻⁶

Heavy metals, such as cadmium, mercury and lead metal-organic compounds such as methyl mercury and toxic organic compounds such as phenol derivatives are considered to be the offending substances, in the effluents. Lagness⁷ reported the toxicity in cases of acute poisoning by heavy metals increased notably with rising water temperature, causing the mortality rate of fish to rise abruptly. This paper reports on the effects of injection of polluted sea water into sample eggs on the growth of chicken fetus and vital tissues.

Materials and Methods

Nest eggs laid of pedigreed white leghorn, (ca 50g) were incubated in an electric lateral incubator equipped with an automatic regulator, between 101°-103°F, and 50-60% humidity. Prior to placement in the incubator all the eggs were cleansed of filth remaining on the shell and sterilized with ethyl alcohol at one end, where drilling was performed for a small aperture, through which polluted sea water for the test was injected into the albumen with a tuberculin syringe. One ml of the sea water used for each of the eggs other than the control eggs, for which 1 ml of unpolluted sea water was used instead.

Incubation was started immediately thereafter. On the 5th day of incubation, the eggs were examined and unimpregnated and dead ones were removed from the incubator. On the 13th day, 5 sample eggs were taken out broken from their shells and weight of fetus and liver as well as water contents of the lungs and allantoic sac were studied and noted. The same procedure was repeated thereafter on the 15th and 17th days, each time taking out a fresh group of 5 eggs. A torsion balance was used to measure liver weight, and ion test paper supplied by Toyo Co., was employed to measure the pH of the allantoic sac water. The sea water used in the experiment was collected from a polluted area of the Seto Inland Sea. Prior to injection in the eggs albumen,

the sea water was analysed for organic matters and heavy metals and some of its properties noted.

S.S : The suspended substances in the sea water were filtered and weighted.

Phenol and its derivative : After adjusting the pH of the samples at 9.0 with aqueous ammonia solution the samples were treated with 4-aminoantipyrine in the presence of potassium ferrocyanide and colour developed was determined spectrophotometrically at 517 nm.

COD : The oxygen defund of the sea water was estimated by titrating aliquotes at boiling temperature with *N*/40 potassium fermate.

Cd, Cr, Pb, and Hg : Cadmium, Chromium, lead and mercury and in the sea water determined by a Mark II atomic absorption spectrophotometer, type AA-I Nippon Jarrell-Ash at the following wave lengths 3579 Å for Cr, 2170 Å for Pb, 2287 Å for Cd, and 2536 Å for Hg. Table 1 shows the results.

TABLE 1—THE IMPURITIES IN THE SEA WATER

	pH	Suspension Solution (ppm)	COD	Phenol and Derivation (ppm)	Total Cr (ppm)	Pb (ppm)
Exp 1	6.6	14.0	79.0	2.1	0.18	0.17
Exp 2	6.9	31.0	38.0	2.3	0.14	0.26

Fetuses subjected to pathological examination were fixed in a 10% formalin solution, buried in paraffin and were treated by hematoxylin-eosin staining.

Results and Discussion

Effect on the liver : Average weights of liver taken on the 13th, 15th, and 17th days, respectively, are give in Table 2.

TABLE 2—GROWTH INHIBITING EFFECT OF SEA WATER POLLUTION ON FETUS LIVER TISSUE (MG)

Experiment No	Control	Exp 1	Exp 2
Average Weight of Liver			
13th day	113.4	105.1	102.7
15th day	287.5	191.4	188.7
17th day	493.1	387.5	379.1

Compared with the weights of liver of the control, those of the samples from eggs injected with polluted sea water show a trend of decrease with increased amounts of pollutants such as of phenol and heavy metals contained in the injected sea water. The results after the 17th day indicate that the growth of the liver in the sea water-treated fetuses was retarded by more than 100 mg as compared with that in the control.

Effect on the lungs: The effects of the sea water pollution on the lungs were examined by taking average lung weight on the 13th, 15th, and 17th days of incubation, respectively. The results are listed in Table 3.

TABLE 3—INHIBITORY EFFECTS OF SEA WATER POLLUTION ON LUNGS GROWTH (MG)

Experiment No		Control	Exp 1	Exp 2
Average Weight of Lungs	13th day	83.0	57.4	49.7
	15th day	134.0	101.4	92.7
	17th day	197.0	117.5	101.3

The above results show considerable inhibition on the growth of fetal lungs due to sea water pollution, when compared with the control.

Allantoic Solution: Increase in the quantities of organic materials and heavy metals contained in the sea water caused clouding in allantoic sea water, accompanied by a decrease in allantoic sac water excretion. The rise of fetal mortality was presumably due to hydropsy and evisceration. As evident from Table IV, the pH of the allantoic solution was reduced, and various deformities appeared, notably twisting of the neck to the right or appearance of short-neck, distortion of vertebra and incapacitation of joint extension with common incidences of extremely dwarfed types. In particular, fetuses injected with sea

TABLE 4—EXCRETION OF ALLANTOIC SOLUTION AND PH

Incubating days	Excretion Grade (ml)			PH		
	13th	15th	17th	13th	15th	17th
Control	8.2	7.2	3.4	7.4	6.9	6.2
	8.7	6.5	2.9	7.4	6.3	6.1
	7.8	6.9	2.6	7.6	6.4	6.0
	8.1	7.0	3.1	7.6	6.0	6.3
	7.9	6.7	3.2	7.5	6.3	6.1
Average	8.14	6.86	3.04	7.50	6.38	6.14
Standard Deviation	0.31	0.24	0.24	0.08	0.29	0.10
Exp 1	8.2	6.7	2.7	7.0	5.8	5.7
	7.5	6.3	2.8	6.3	5.3	5.8
	7.7	6.2	2.9	6.8	5.9	5.7
	7.9	6.5	2.4	6.8	5.7	5.6
	7.7	6.8	2.6	7.2	5.6	5.8
Average	7.80	6.50	2.68	6.82	5.66	5.72
Standard Deviation	0.23	0.22	0.38	0.35	0.20	0.25
Exp 2	7.7	5.3	2.9	7.0	5.5	5.9
	7.8	5.9	3.1	6.9	5.3	5.4
	7.3	4.4	2.4	6.0	5.5	5.1
	7.6	5.3	2.8	6.4	5.4	5.5
	7.4	4.7	2.6	6.1	5.0	5.7
Average	7.56	5.12	2.76	6.48	5.34	5.52
Standard Deviation	0.18	0.52	0.19	0.40	0.18	0.27

water containing chromium or lead caused not only deformities, but also many cases of hydropsy and evisceration which contributed to increased mortality.

Change in body weight: As shown in Table 5, body weight of the control fetuses increased as incubation progressed. Among the fetuses injected with sea

TABLE 5—EFFECTS OF POLLUTED SEA WATER ON GROWTH OF CHICKEN FETUS (G)

Incubating days	13th	15th	17th
Control	5.3	12.0	23.8
	4.9	12.7	24.0
	5.3	14.1	23.7
	5.2	14.3	23.9
	5.0	14.3	22.5
Average	5.14	13.48	23.80
Standard Deviation	0.15	0.95	0.59
Exp 1	5.0	10.6	20.1
	4.3	11.8	15.8
	4.0	11.5	19.3
	4.1	10.3	17.8
	5.3	11.1	18.9
Average	4.54	11.60	18.38
Standard Deviation	0.50	0.77	1.48
Exp 2	4.3	10.2	19.3
	4.1	10.5	17.4
	4.7	11.2	18.6
	4.2	10.3	18.1
	4.0	10.7	18.6
Average	4.26	10.58	18.50
Standard Deviation	0.24	0.35	0.63

water containing organic matters and heavy metals, there were cases that developed hydropsy and evisceration on about the 13th day of incubation, frequently resulting in death of the fetus.

Histological Discussion: On the 13th day of both the control and contaminated fetuses showed lung-pipes surrounded by rough connective tissues at about the center of the vascular retinal eyes. Although the tissue constituting the lung-pipes increased, the formation of abnormal protuberances on the lungs did not appear, in the wide smooth layer adhering to the bottom surrounded the whole lung-pipes. On the 15th day of incubation, the control exhibited spreading of the lung-pipes, rising of protuberance occurring through the smooth muscle layer, and the base was found to be wide. Slight labyrinth capillary pervasion was observed, while the surrounding rough tissue became less obvious. In contrast, the lung-pipe proliferation in contaminated fetuses was not obvious. Those lung-pipe cells exhibited retarded multiplication and the rising protuberance, though visible, did not penetrate the smooth muscle perfectly.

Furthermore, no labyrinth formation could be detected. Growth-inhibited capillaries had also resulted in anemia. The interstitial tissue was mostly of rough-connective nature. On the 17th day of incubation, the lung-pipes of the control fetuses showed expansion, the basal cavity of the protuberance was wide, the labyrinth formation was perfect, and capillary growth

Control

Sea Water

13th Day

15th Day

17th Day

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showed vigor and pervasion. In contrast, contaminated fetuses showed no observable increase in the protuberance, nor was any labyrinth formation to be noted. They showed, poor capillary formation with accompanying anemia. Thus, from above experiments it is concluded that polluted sea water causes growth inhibition in chicken embryos and interferes with normal tissue development.

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